

Toward Metadata-Driven Experimentation in Software Engineering: A Vision for Reproducible, Interoperable, and Transparent Research

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Abstract

Empirical Software Engineering increasingly relies on controlled experimentation, yet current reproducibility practices focus primarily on artifact availability rather than on how experimental knowledge is represented and reused at scale. As a result, many experiments remain reproducible in principle but difficult to interpret, compare, and integrate across contexts and time. This position paper argues that this gap constitutes a structural challenge for the future of Software Engineering and proposes metadata-driven experimentation as an evolution of existing reproducibility practices, treating experimental metadata and conceptual structure as first-class research artifacts. By enabling structured, machine-interpretable representations of experimental intent, design, context, and analysis, metadata complements narrative reporting and executable artifacts, supporting cumulative knowledge building and scalable empirical research in the coming decade.

CCS Concepts

• **General and reference** → **Experimentation; Empirical studies; • Software and its engineering;**

Keywords

Empirical Software Engineering, Controlled Experimentation, Reproducibility, Metadata-Driven Experimentation, Metadata, Research Infrastructure, Cumulative Knowledge

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1 Introduction

Software Engineering has long aspired to be an evidence-based discipline. Controlled experimentation plays a central role in this aspiration by enabling researchers to isolate factors, measure effects, and reason about causality. Foundational methodological

work has emphasized that reliable and actionable knowledge in Software Engineering should emerge cumulatively, through coordinated replications and families of experiments, rather than through isolated empirical results that are difficult to relate and synthesize across contexts [1]. At the same time, the community has repeatedly reflected on its own research practices, recognizing that scientific progress depends not only on new techniques and tools, but also on the robustness, transparency, and scalability of the research infrastructure itself [7].

In recent years, these reflections have materialized into concrete actions. ICSE and related venues have invested heavily in reproducibility initiatives, including artifact evaluation tracks, badging schemes, and stronger expectations for sharing data, code, scripts, and supplementary material. These initiatives have led to measurable cultural change. Today, sharing artifacts is increasingly perceived as a core scientific responsibility rather than an optional add-on, and many researchers invest significant effort in packaging, archiving, and documenting their experimental materials.

Despite this progress, a fundamental misalignment remains unresolved. Current reproducibility initiatives primarily optimize for artifact availability rather than for experimental intelligibility, comparability, and scalability of reuse. As a result, many experiments are reproducible in principle, yet remain difficult to understand, adapt, or integrate into broader bodies of evidence in practice. Experimental knowledge is still largely encoded in narrative descriptions, informal conventions, and implicit assumptions scattered across papers, appendices, README files, and repositories.

This paper takes a clear position. Artifact availability, while necessary, is no longer sufficient for sustaining empirical Software Engineering as a cumulative scientific discipline. We argue that the community must move beyond narrative-centric representations of experiments and adopt metadata-driven experimentation as a first-class research practice. By metadata-driven experimentation, we mean the explicit, structured, and machine-interpretable representation of experimental intent, design, context, execution, and analysis, maintained alongside artifacts throughout the research lifecycle.

2 Background and Motivation

2.1 Experimentation, Reproducibility, and Structural Limits

Controlled experimentation in Software Engineering involves defining research questions and hypotheses, selecting variables and treatments, designing tasks and instruments, recruiting participants or

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selecting datasets, executing procedures, and analyzing results. Established guidance emphasizes precise operational definitions, careful control of confounding factors, and transparent documentation to support validity [14].

The long-term scientific value of experiments increases when studies can be replicated, compared, and aggregated across contexts. The notion of families of experiments explicitly recognizes that individual experiments rarely provide definitive answers on their own. Instead, knowledge emerges through coordinated replications that systematically vary contextual factors [1]. Achieving this vision requires that experimental constructs, assumptions, and procedures are represented in ways that other researchers can interpret consistently and operationalize reliably.

Artifact evaluation and open sharing are necessary foundations for reproducibility, but they are often insufficient for effective reuse and synthesis [8]. Empirical studies show that while artifact availability has increased, challenges related to understandability, accessibility, and long-term preservation remain [5]. Even when artifacts are available, researchers often struggle to reuse them due to missing contextual information and undocumented assumptions [13].

3 Problem Statement

Despite sustained progress in artifact sharing, a structural gap persists between making experimental artifacts available and making them interpretable, comparable, and reusable in practice [6]. Experimental protocols are often described at a high level of abstraction, with operational details scattered across papers and repositories. Contextual information, such as the execution environment, participant characteristics, or dataset provenance, is frequently underspecified [3, 4].

Traceability between claims and evidence remains fragile. Reviewers and readers often struggle to identify which scripts, parameters, or outputs underpin specific reported results. Replication studies frequently diverge from original designs in undocumented ways, making differences difficult to interpret.

4 Vision: Metadata-Driven Experimentation

Metadata-driven experimentation rethinks how experimental knowledge is represented, communicated, and preserved [11]. Rather than treating experiments solely as narrative descriptions accompanied by executable artifacts, this vision treats experiments as structured entities whose core methodological elements are explicitly modeled and shared.

Metadata captures experimental intent, design choices, contextual assumptions, and analytical pathways in a form that can be interpreted by both humans and tools [10]. Structured representations make explicit what is currently implicit, reducing ambiguity and supporting reliable interpretation and reuse.

Metadata-driven experimentation does not aim to standardize experimental design. Narrative reporting remains essential. Instead, metadata provides a shared backbone that externalizes experimental structure, allowing diverse experiments to be related and aggregated without constraining methodological diversity.

5 Positioning Within the Future of Software Engineering

The Future of Software Engineering track has historically served as a forum for identifying structural challenges that shape the long-term evolution of the discipline, beyond incremental technical improvements. Contributions to FOSE have emphasized the importance of research infrastructure, community practices, and methodological foundations as first-order concerns for sustaining scientific progress [7].

This paper is explicitly aligned with that tradition. We argue that metadata-driven experimentation addresses a structural challenge that will increasingly define the future of empirical Software Engineering: the inability of narrative-centric experimental reporting to scale with the growing volume, diversity, and automation of research [12]. While recent reproducibility initiatives have substantially improved the availability of artifacts, they have not fundamentally changed how experimental knowledge is represented, interpreted, or integrated across studies.

From a FOSE perspective, this limitation is not merely a matter of documentation quality. It reflects a deeper tension between the scale at which empirical research is now produced and the representational mechanisms inherited from an earlier era, when experiments were fewer, smaller, and primarily interpreted by close-knit research communities. As Software Engineering continues to grow as a global and heterogeneous discipline, reliance on implicit assumptions encoded in prose becomes increasingly fragile.

Metadata-driven experimentation responds to this challenge by reframing experimental knowledge as shared infrastructure rather than as paper-specific narrative. By making experimental intent, design, context, and analysis explicit and structured, metadata enables new modes of interaction between researchers, tools, and venues. This shift is essential to supporting long-term goals that FOSE has repeatedly highlighted, including the cumulative evidence-building, scalable replication, and methodological transparency.

5.1 Scalability, Automation, and the Next Decade of Empirical SE

A defining characteristic of the future of Software Engineering research is scale. Publication volumes continue to increase, empirical methods diversify, and expectations for openness and reuse become more stringent. At the same time, reviewer capacity and community bandwidth do not scale proportionally. FOSE discussions have repeatedly emphasized that sustaining rigor under these conditions requires rethinking not only techniques, but also the underlying research infrastructure.

Metadata-driven experimentation directly addresses this scalability challenge. Structured experimental metadata supports partial automation in areas such as protocol validation, reviewer support, experiment discovery, and secondary study preparation. These capabilities are increasingly important as artificial intelligence and automated analysis tools become integral to the research lifecycle.

However, such tools depend critically on structured, machine-interpretable representations. AI systems can reason effectively from explicit representations of experimental design and context, but struggle with implicit assumptions embedded in narrative text. Without metadata-driven representations, the potential of AI-assisted

reviewing, large-scale experiment mining, and automated synthesis remains severely limited.

From a FOSE standpoint, metadata-driven experimentation is therefore not an optional enhancement. It is a prerequisite for enabling the next generation of research assistance tools and for ensuring that empirical Software Engineering can evolve as a scalable scientific enterprise.

5.2 Implications for Research Culture and Community Practices

FOSE has consistently highlighted that the future of Software Engineering is shaped as much by sociotechnical practices as by technical innovation. Metadata-driven experimentation exemplifies this perspective. Its success does not depend solely on new schemas or tools, but on gradual shifts in how the community values and evaluates experimental contributions.

By treating experimental metadata and conceptual structure as first-class artifacts, the community makes methodological intent more visible, review processes more transparent, and reuse more achievable [6]. This shift aligns naturally with existing ICSE incentives, particularly artifact evaluation, while addressing persistent challenges related to reviewer burden, replication ambiguity, and secondary study costs.

Importantly, metadata-driven experimentation does not require abandoning narrative reporting or constraining methodological diversity. Instead, it complements existing practices by externalizing experimental structure in ways that support both human understanding and tool-based analysis. This balance between expressiveness and structure is essential for long-term adoption and resonates strongly with FOSE’s emphasis on pragmatic, evidence-driven evolution.

6 Building Blocks of the Proposed Solution

Metadata-driven experimentation relies on conceptual models, metadata profiles, and tool-supported representations that integrate with existing workflows.

Conceptual models provide shared abstractions for experimental activities, artifacts, and relationships. Metadata profiles tailored to Software Engineering experiments build on these models, capturing domain-specific aspects such as tools as treatments, codebases as tasks, and context-sensitive execution environments.

Ontologies and machine-interpretable representations add semantic precision and enable automated discovery and validation. However, author-facing representations must remain lightweight, with tools generating richer semantic representations as needed.

6.1 Conceptual Overview and Rationale for Using Dublin Core

A central design decision in the proposed metadata-driven experimentation approach concerns the choice of a foundational metadata framework. We deliberately ground our proposal in Dublin Core rather than introducing a bespoke, fully domain-specific schema. This choice is motivated by long-term sustainability, interoperability, and alignment with Open Science and FAIR principles, all of which are central concerns in the Future of Software Engineering perspective.

Open Science emphasizes transparency, reuse, and the long-term accessibility of research outputs beyond individual publications. FAIR principles further operationalize these goals by requiring that research artifacts and their associated metadata are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Within this context, metadata is not an auxiliary concern, but a prerequisite for enabling openness at scale. Without stable, shared, and interoperable metadata foundations, Open Science practices remain fragmented and difficult to sustain over time.

Dublin Core provides a minimal, stable, and widely adopted set of metadata elements for describing digital resources across domains [2, 10]. Its cross-disciplinary acceptance and long-term stability make it particularly suitable as an infrastructural layer for experimental metadata that is expected to persist, evolve, and be reused across venues, communities, and technological generations [12]. In contrast, narrowly scoped or ad hoc schemas often exhibit limited adoption, weak interoperability, and rapid obsolescence, undermining FAIR goals even when artifacts are openly shared.

Importantly, grounding metadata-driven experimentation in Dublin Core does not impose methodological standardization or constrain experimental design. Instead, it establishes a shared infrastructural anchor that stabilizes experimental descriptions while allowing Software Engineering specific extensions to evolve incrementally. This separation between stable core metadata and evolving domain-specific profiles mirrors Open Science best practices, where shared infrastructure supports diversity rather than enforcing uniformity.

By aligning experimental metadata with a widely adopted and Open Science compatible standard, metadata-driven experimentation avoids becoming an isolated technical initiative. Instead, it integrates experimental knowledge into the same ecosystem that already manages publications, datasets, and software artifacts. This integration is essential for long-term preservation, cross-venue aggregation, and the accumulation of evidence, all of which are fundamental to the future of empirical Software Engineering.

Figure 1 illustrates this role of Dublin Core as a foundational layer that bridges narrative reports, executable artifacts, and Software Engineering specific experimental metadata. In this architecture, Dublin Core provides the stable descriptive backbone required by Open Science and FAIR principles, while domain-specific extensions capture experimental intent, design, context, and analysis in structured and reusable forms.

This alignment between metadata-driven experimentation, Open Science, and FAIR principles has direct implications for community action. Treating experimental metadata as a first-class research artifact requires collective commitment rather than isolated adoption. Authors must be encouraged to explicitly expose the experimental structure, artifact evaluators must be equipped to assess this structure systematically, and venues must recognize structured metadata as an essential component of experimental contributions. By grounding this effort in a widely adopted and FAIR-compatible foundation such as Dublin Core, the community can act incrementally while ensuring that individual contributions accumulate into shared, long-lived research infrastructure. This perspective directly motivates the call to action articulated in the final section of this paper.

Figure 1: Conceptual overview of metadata-driven experimentation.

6.2 Minimal Metadata Profiles

To make metadata-driven experimentation viable at the ICSE scale, a minimal yet expressive metadata scope is required. The goal is to preserve methodological meaning without encoding every experimental detail.

At a minimum, metadata should capture experiment identification and provenance, research intent, experimental design, subjects or datasets, tasks and instrumentation, execution environment, analysis plans, traceability, threats to validity, and dissemination conditions.

6.3 Illustrative Metadata Encodings

Figures 2 and 3 illustrate lightweight XML-based representations inspired by Dublin Core profiles [9–12]. The first figure focuses on descriptive experimental metadata, while the second extends this profile with elements that explicitly support reproducibility and traceability.

These examples illustrate how experimental intent, design, context, and analysis can be represented explicitly and consistently, complementing narrative descriptions and executable artifacts.

7 Alignment with ICSE Incentives and Processes

Metadata-driven experimentation aligns naturally with ICSE artifact evaluation, replication research, and peer review practices. Structured metadata reduces reviewer effort, improves consistency, and supports more systematic assessment of experimental rigor. It also strengthens replication studies by making experimental structure explicit and comparable, thereby operationalizing the vision of families of experiments [1].

8 Roadmap for Adoption

Adoption should be incremental. In the short term, volunteer artifacts can be accompanied by lightweight metadata templates and validation tools. In the medium term, metadata can be integrated into artifact evaluation workflows as optional reviewer aids. In

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<resource:experiment xmlns:dc=
"http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/">
  <dc:subject:analysis>
    <dc:description:descriptive.statistics>
      Descriptive statistics were calculated for
      participant size ratings and collected size
      metrics, including mean, median, and standard
      deviation. Most participants rated PLA
      reusability as high or extremely high, while
      metric values were mostly in the range of 4 to 7
      operations per class.
    </dc:description:descriptive.statistics>
    <dc:description.data.set.reduction>
      Conversion of Likert-scale labels into numeric
      values (-2 to +2)
    </dc:description.data.set.reduction>
    <dc:description.hypothesis.testing>
      The Spearman correlation test was applied,
      resulting in a weak positive correlation
      (0.3937237) between size metrics and participant
      size ratings, allowing rejection of H0 with 95%
      confidence and providing initial evidence that
      size metrics can be used to assess PLA
      reusability.
    </dc:description.hypothesis.testing>
  </dc:subject:analysis>
</resource:experiment>
```

Figure 2: Excerpt of a Dublin Core-based profile for describing a controlled experiment.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<resource:reproducibility xmlns:dc=
"http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/">
  <dc:subject:methodology>
    <dc:description:capture>
      <dc:description.steps>
        Dataset construction, creation and execution of
        the script in the R language, and recording of
        the results
      </dc:description.steps>
      <dc:description.activities>
        Study of size and reusability concepts,
        evaluation of SPL architectures,
        and recording of results; initialization of
        SDMetrics, file loading,
        and export of calculations.
      </dc:description.activities>
    </dc:description:capture>
    <dc:description:extraction>
      <dc:description.steps>Identification and recording.
      </dc:description.steps>
      <dc:description.activities>
        Identification of the number of operations per
        class and automatic
        recording of the results calculated by
        SDMetrics.
      </dc:description.activities>
    </dc:description:extraction>
    <dc:description:analysis>
      <dc:description.tests>Spearman correlation test.
      </dc:description.tests>
      <dc:description.steps>
        Dataset construction, creation and execution of
        the R algorithm,
        and recording of results.
      </dc:description.steps>
      <dc:description.activities>
        Creation of an R script, application of the
        correlation test,
        and recording of results.
      </dc:description.activities>
    </dc:description:analysis>
    <dc:description:validation>
      <dc:description.steps>
        Identification and removal of issues.
      </dc:description.steps>
      <dc:description.activities>
        Detection and removal of outlier or missing
        values in the datasets.
      </dc:description.activities>
    </dc:description:validation>
  </dc:subject:methodology>
</resource:reproducibility>
```

Figure 3: Excerpt of an extended Dublin Core-based profile supporting reproducibility and traceability.

the long term, stable metadata profiles and shared registries can support discovery, replication, and synthesis across venues and years.

9 Call to Action

As empirical Software Engineering continues to grow in scale, diversity, and societal relevance, sustaining trust and cumulative knowledge requires more than sharing code and data. It requires preserving experimental meaning in structured, interoperable, and reusable forms that remain intelligible beyond individual papers, venues, and research groups. Metadata-driven experimentation addresses this need by elevating experimental metadata and conceptual structure to the status of first-class research artifacts.

We call on the Software Engineering community to recognize that FAIR principles, artifact evaluation, and replication research are not independent initiatives, but mutually reinforcing mechanisms. Artifact evaluation operationalizes openness and rigor at submission time, FAIR principles ensure long-term discoverability and reuse, and replication studies test the robustness and generalizability of experimental claims over time. Structured and interoperable experimental metadata provides the connective layer that enables these mechanisms to reinforce one another and scale across venues and years.

For authors, this implies a shift in how experimental contributions are conceived and communicated. Beyond reporting results and sharing artifacts, authors should explicitly expose experimental intent, design choices, contextual assumptions, and analysis pathways in structured forms that complement narrative descriptions. Doing so not only improves transparency and reproducibility but also increases the long-term value and reuse potential of experimental work.

For artifact evaluators and reviewers, metadata-driven experimentation offers an opportunity to move from interpretive reconstruction toward systematic assessment. Structured metadata can reduce reviewer burden, improve consistency across evaluations, and make methodological assumptions more visible under strict page and time constraints. We encourage evaluation processes to treat structured experimental metadata as an aid to judgment rather than as an additional compliance requirement.

For tool builders and infrastructure providers, metadata-driven experimentation creates opportunities for innovation. Validation tools, metadata-aware artifact packaging, experiment discovery services, and AI-assisted review support all depend on explicit and machine-interpretable representations of experimental knowledge. Without such representations, the potential of automation and intelligent assistance in empirical research remains severely limited.

From a Future of Software Engineering perspective, metadata-driven experimentation is not a marginal enhancement to current practices. It is an investment in the next decade of empirical research, one that enables scalability, supports cumulative knowledge building, and prepares the discipline for a research ecosystem increasingly shaped by automation and collective intelligence. The question is no longer whether structured experimental metadata is desirable, but whether empirical Software Engineering can afford to continue without it.

10 Final Remarks

This paper argues that, despite significant progress in artifact sharing, reproducibility initiatives have not fundamentally addressed how experimental knowledge in Software Engineering is represented, interpreted, and reused at scale. As empirical output grows and automation increasingly shapes the research lifecycle, narrative-centric reporting alone is insufficient to support cumulative knowledge building.

We positioned metadata-driven experimentation as a structural response to this limitation. By externalizing experimental intent, design, context, and analysis in structured and interoperable forms, metadata complements narrative reports and executable artifacts, improving intelligibility, comparability, and long-term reuse. Grounding this approach in widely adopted standards such as Dublin Core aligns experimental metadata with Open Science and FAIR principles while preserving methodological diversity.

From a Future of Software Engineering perspective, metadata-driven experimentation should be treated as shared research infrastructure rather than auxiliary documentation. Elevating experimental metadata to a first-class artifact enables scalable review, systematic replication, and emerging forms of tool and AI-assisted support. Advancing empirical Software Engineering as a cumulative and scalable discipline, therefore, requires embracing structured experimental metadata as a long-term community investment.

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References

- [1] Victor R. Basili, Forrest Shull, and Filippo Lanubile. 1999. Building Knowledge through Families of Experiments. *IEEE Tran. Sof. Eng.* 25, 4 (1999), 456–473.
- [2] DCMI. 2025. Dublin Core. <https://www.dublincore.org/about/> Acessado em 13 de Maio de 2025.
- [3] Jesús M González-Barahona and Gregorio Robles. 2012. On the reproducibility of empirical software engineering studies based on data retrieved from development repositories. *Empirical Software Engineering* 17, 1 (2012), 75–89.
- [4] Jesus M Gonzalez-Barahona and Gregorio Robles. 2023. Revisiting the reproducibility of empirical software engineering studies based on data retrieved from development repositories. *Inf. Sof. Tech.* 164 (2023), 107318.
- [5] Robert Heumüller et al. 2020. Publish or Perish, but Do Not Forget Your Software Artifacts. *Emp. Sof. Eng.* 25 (2020), 4580–4626.
- [6] Edson Oliveira Jr et al. 2024. A Vision on Open Science for the Evolution of Software Engineering Research and Practice. In *FSE*. doi:10.1145/3663529.3663788
- [7] Dewayne E. Perry, Adam A. Porter, and Lawrence G. Votta. 2000. Empirical Studies of Software Engineering: A Roadmap. In *FOSE*. 345–355.
- [8] Sheeba Samuel and Birgitta König-Ries. 2021. Understanding experiments and research practices for reproducibility: an exploratory study. *PeerJ* 9 (2021).
- [9] Filipe Santana, André Cordeiro, and Edson Oliveira Jr. 2023. Dublin Core for Recording Metadata of Software Engineering Experiments: A Survey. In *Regional School of Software Engineering*. SBC, 169–177. doi:10.5753/eres.2023.237790
- [10] Filipe Santana, André Cordeiro, and Edson Oliveira Jr. 2023. Using the Dublin Core Standard to Express Open Metadata for Software Engineering Experiments. In *OpenScienSE*. SBC, 1–5. doi:10.5753/openscience.2023.235672
- [11] Filipe Santana, André Cordeiro, and Edson Oliveira Jr. 2024. Investigating Computational Solutions for Metadata Processing in Software Engineering Experiments. In *Regional School of Software Engineering*. SBC, 1–10. doi:10.5753/eres.2024.4283
- [12] Filipe A. Santana, André F. R. Cordeiro, and Edson Oliveira Jr. 2025. DCEP-SE: A Dublin Core Application Profile for Experimental Software Engineering. In *Regional School of Software Engineering*. SBC, Chapeçó, SC, Brazil.
- [13] Christopher S Timperley, Lauren Herckis, Claire Le Goues, and Michael Hilton. 2021. Understanding and Improving Artifact Sharing in Software Engineering Research. *Emp. Sof. Eng.* 26 (2021), 1–41.
- [14] Claes Wohlin, Per Runeson, Martin Höst, Magnus C. Ohlsson, Björn Regnell, and Anders Wesslén. 2012. *Experimentation in Software Engineering*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.